

References

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4-(2-Pyridylazo)naphthol—An Amperometric Reagent for Trace Determination of Gallium(III), Indium(III) and Thallium(I)

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AMONG the various heterocyclic azo dyes¹⁻⁴, PAN, PAR and TAR have been satisfactorily used for the spectrophotometric determination of rare earths. Recently in our laboratory, current-voltage behaviour of such azo dyes has been investigated and the dyes used as amperometric reagents⁵⁻⁸. The spectrophotometric method is not suitable when precipitation occurs, nor it can be used at the close proximity of the wavelength of adsorption of complex and ligand. The present paper deals with the use of 4-(2-pyridylazo)naphthol (PAN) for the trace determination of the titled metal ions. The method is fairly sensitive and accurate.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR or extrapure quality. Solutions of metal ions, viz. Ga⁺⁺⁺, In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I were prepared by dissolving a calculated amount of the metal nitrate in double-distilled water and standardised by EDTA⁹. The solution of PAN was prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of the reagent in double-distilled water. Amperometric titrations were performed on a manually operated polarograph with a multiflex galvanometer (sensitivity 8.1×10^{-9} A/div), used to measure the current. A d.m.e. and a saturated

calomel electrode were used as an indicator and reference electrode, respectively. The capillary used for d.m.e. had a value of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.316 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$. The amperometric titrations were performed at room temperature $30 \pm 1^\circ$. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used to measure the pH of the test solutions.

Polarographic behaviour of metal ions: Each of the Ga⁺⁺⁺, In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I gave a very well defined reduction wave in 0.1 M KCl at pH 4.0 + 0.02. The diffusion current for each wave is proportional to the concentration of the metal. PAN did not give any wave under the said experimental conditions.

For titrations, sets of solutions containing known amount of PAN in 0.3 M KCl as supporting electrolyte were prepared and pH of each set was adjusted to 4.0 ± 0.02 . The titrations with each of the metal ions as titrant were carried out separately at -0.6 V vs S.C.E. in case of In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I, and at -1.20 V vs S.C.E. with Ga⁺⁺⁺, respectively (the mentioned potentials being the plateau potentials of respective reduction waves of In⁺⁺⁺, Tl^I and Ga⁺⁺⁺). Reversed L-shaped curves were obtained on plotting galvanometer deflection against the volume of titrant added. The end-point indicated metal-PAN ratio of 1:2 in each case. The L-shaped curves may be obtained using the metal solution as titrate and PAN as titrant.

Results and Discussion

The titrations were not hampered by the presence of various foreign ions viz. chloride, iodide, acetate, nitrate, chlorate, sulphate, Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Mg⁺⁺ and Ca⁺⁺ etc. However, a small amount of carbonate, phosphate, Cu⁺⁺, Cd⁺⁺, Ni⁺⁺, Pd⁺⁺, Fe⁺⁺⁺, Sb⁺⁺⁺, and rare earths etc. seriously interfered the titration procedure.

The results of amperometric estimations of the titled metal ions with PAN are presented in Table 1. The results indicate that the PAN is a good amperometric reagent for the trace determination of Ga⁺⁺⁺, In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I. Amounts as low as 69.85 ppm of Ga⁺⁺⁺, 114.8 ppm of In⁺⁺⁺ and 204.3 ppm

TABLE—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Ga⁺⁺⁺, In⁺⁺⁺ AND Tl^I WITH PANPlateau potential = -1.20 V vs S.C.E. with Ga⁺⁺⁺, -0.65 V vs S.C.E. with In⁺⁺⁺ and Tl^I
I = 0.3 M (KCl), pH = 4.0 + 0.02, Temp. = 30 + 1°

Sl no.	Amount of Ga ⁺⁺⁺ (ppm)		% Error	Amount of In ⁺⁺⁺ (ppm)		% Error	Amount of Tl ^I (ppm)		% Error
	Taken	Found		Taken	Found		Taken	Found	
1.	69.72	69.82	+0.18	114.8	115.8	+0.87	204.3	204.5	+0.098
2.	174.20	173.00	-0.69	287.00	286.2	-0.27	510.7	512.5	-0.35
3.	348.50	346.00	-0.71	574.00	576.8	+0.48	1 021.5	1 029.6	+0.86
4.	512.70	516.80	+0.80	861.00	860.0	-0.12	1 531.1	1 536.9	+0.47
5.	697.20	693.00	-0.60	1 148.00	1 150.0	+0.17	2 045.7	2 042.0	-0.18
6.	1 045.70	1 049.00	+0.31	1 722.00	1 718.0	-0.23	3 065.0	3 065.0	+0.23

Standard deviation (%): Ga, 0.045; In, 0.05; Tl, 0.088.
Coefficient of variation: Ga, 0.64; In, 0.43; Tl, 0.45.

of Tl^I could be successfully titrated amperometrically within an error limit of less than $+0.8\%$. The experimental and calculated statistical data prove the utility of the proposed analytical procedure.

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Chromatography of certain Metal Ions on Ligand combined Ion-exchange Papers

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CHROMATOGRAPHY on papers treated with inorganic ion-exchangers¹⁻⁴ has proved to be important particularly for ionic species, as the separations are mainly based on the intrinsic selectivity of the ion-exchanger itself. Use of ligands in combination with the ion exchange material may prove it of further importance to increase the selectivity⁵. Bayer⁶ perhaps is the first to study the effect of water-soluble ligands on selectivity of ion-exchanger, because the ligands acquire a definite attachment with the matrix of the exchanger. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid can be proved to be a good example in this process. One useful advantage of this reagent is that it forms 1:1 complexes practically instantaneously with most cations regardless of their oxidation states. Therefore, the chromatographic studies of a number of

cations on papers treated with a ligand combined ion-exchanger are reported in this manuscript.

Experimental

Chromatography was performed on Whatman No. 1 Paper strips (14×3 cm) in glass jars (20×5 cm). Chemicals and solvents were of analytical reagent grade.

Preparation of ion-exchange paper: Aqueous solutions (0.1 M) of zinc nitrate and sodium silicate were prepared. The paper strips were first dipped in zinc nitrate solution for 3–5 s and the excess reagent was drained off. The strips were then dipped in sodium silicate solution for 15 s, the excess reagent was drained off, and dried at room temperature. The zinc silicate impregnated paper was made to the EDTA-form by dipping in 1% EDTA solution for 10–15 s and then drying at room temperature. Similarly, the zinc silicate impregnated strips were dipped in 1.0 M NH_3 solution to convert them to NH_3 -form.

Test solution: Most of the cation solutions in chloride, nitrate and sulphate forms of 0.1 M concentration were prepared in water. The solutions of mercuric nitrate and chromium nitrate were prepared in 0.1 M HNO_3 . Pr, Ho, Gd, Dy and Nd solutions were prepared in alcohol. Bismuth chloride solution was prepared in 7.3 M HCl and ceric sulphate solution in 3.6 N H_2SO_4 .

Detection: Yellow ammonium sulphide was used to detect Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Bi^{3+} . Fe^{3+} was detected with aqueous potassium ferrocyanide solution; Mg^{2+} with ethanolic solution of quinalizarine; Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Cr^{3+} with 1% diphenylcarbazide in ethanol solution; ZrO^{2+} , Th^{4+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Ho^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Pr^{3+} with aqueous alizarin red S solution; Al^{3+} and Be^{2+} with 1% ethanolic solution of aluminon. A fresh solution of sodium cobaltinitrite was used for the detection of K^+ and Rb^+ . Ba^{2+} and Sr^{2+} were detected with freshly prepared aqueous sodium rhodizonate solution. 1% ethanolic solution of dimethyl glyoxime was used to detect Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} .

Procedure: Thin glass capillaries were used to spot test-solutions. The strips were conditioned for 15 min and the solvent was allowed to ascend 10 cm on paper. The strips were then dried at room temperature and the detection was made with the respective detecting reagents.

Results and Discussion

A substance may be characterised by determining R_f value R_f of 29 metal ions on EDTA-treated papers using different concentrations of ammonia as the developing solvent are summarised in Table I. A trend of R_f values reveal that most of the metal ions having higher stability constants show lower R_f values while for K^+ and Rb^+ the values are exceptionally higher⁶. This is because the higher the